

Guidelines for co-authors

Performing an internal review

Please consider the following questions when reviewing a section, and feel free to add your own comments:

Status: Does this section:

1. Explain the topic in an accessible way suitable for someone who isn't familiar with it? Y/N
2. Motivate why the topic is important? Y/N
3. (If not) How could this section be improved? ...

Current and Future Challenges: Does this section:

4. Clearly state the challenges associated with this topic? Y/N
5. Include the most important challenges? Y/N
6. (If not) What challenge(s) could be added? ...

Advances in Science and Technology to Meet Challenges: Does this section:

7. Provide directions for future work to address the challenges? Y/N
8. Provide specific ideas for future work which would be helpful for a beginner? Y/N
9. (If not) What idea(s) for future work could be added? ...

10. Please note any other areas for improvement here:

...
...
...

Guidelines for editors

Section:

Title:

1. Does the title describe the topic well? Y/N
2. Could the title be shortened without detriment? Y/N
3. Is the title accessible, without abbreviations? Y/N
4. Please note any suggested changes to the title: ...

Status: Does this section:

5. Explain the topic in an accessible way suitable for someone who isn't familiar with it? Y/N
6. Motivate why the topic is important? Y/N

7. Outline the potential benefit of further advances? Y/N
8. (If not) How could this section be improved? ...

Current and Future Challenges: Does this section:

9. Clearly state the challenges associated with this topic? Y/N
10. Include the most important challenges? Y/N
11. (If not) What challenge(s) could be added? ...

Advances in Science and Technology to Meet Challenges: Does this section:

12. Provide directions for future work to address the challenges? Y/N
13. Provide specific ideas for future work which would be helpful for a beginner? Y/N
14. (If not) What idea(s) for future work could be added? ...

Perspective

15. Is the section written with equipoise (*i.e.* balanced opinions)? Y/N
16. (If not) How could a more balanced perspective be given? ...

Referencing

17. Are any references to unreliable sources? Y/N
18. Are the authors' own works cited excessively? Y/N
19. Are any key references missing? Y/N
20. Are there too many references? Y/N
21. (if so) How could the references be improved? ...

Style

22. Is the section written on the word template provided? Y/N
23. Are all the author details provided (first and last names, institution(s), ORCID(s))? Y/N
24. Is the section of an appropriate length (*i.e.* 2 pages, approx. 1,400 words)? Y/N
25. Is a suitable referencing style used? Y/N
26. Figures: are figures clear with brief but informative captions? Y/N
27. Are all abbreviations defined? Y/N
28. (if any) How could the style be improved? ...

29. Please note any other areas for improvement here:

...
...
...